

THE USE OF TRIPHASIC HYALURONAN-CHITOSAN-STRONTIUM CHLORIDE MEMBRANE IN TREATING INTRABONY DEFECT (RANDOMIZED CLINICAL TRIAL)

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Abstract

Background: The goal of periodontal treatment is to stop this progressive destruction by controlling infection, thus preventing tooth loss. The aim of this work was to evaluate the efficacy of the combined effect of Chitosan, hyaluronan, and strontium chloride membranes in the treatment of periodontal intrabony defect. **Methods:** This research was randomized controlled trial. This study was carried out on 36 patients with an age range between 25 and 55 years. The patients were divided into two equal groups as follows: Group A (Control group): patients were treated with open flap debridement and group B (Test group): patients were treated surgically with hyaluronan, chitosan, and strontium chloride membrane. **Results:** The pain was significantly reduced in group B compared to group A at D1 and D2 ($P < 0.001$), while the remaining durations were insignificantly different between both groups. The gingival index and probing depth was significantly reduced after 3 months and after 6 months compared to baseline in group A and in group B ($P < 0.001$). **Conclusions:** The use of triphasic Hyaluronan – Chitosan – Strontium Chloride membrane in conjunction with periodontal flap surgery in treating intrabony defect did not show a statistically significant difference in comparison to OFD alone. Regarding periodontal probing depth, clinical attachment loss, gingival index, and radiographic bone fill, there was an improvement in both groups. Moreover, tissue response to the triphasic Hyaluronan -Chitosan- Strontium Chloride membrane was favorable as reflected by reduced pain and swelling.

Keywords: Triphasic Hyaluronan, Chitosan, Strontium Chloride Membrane, Intrabony Defect.

INTRODUCTION

In the field of dental health, periodontal diseases stand as a principal cause of tooth loss, presenting a significant challenge for both patients and dental practitioners. These conditions, characterized by an inflammatory response within the periodontium, can lead to the destruction of tooth-supporting structures, necessitating interventions that go beyond conventional treatment paradigms ^[1].

The goal of periodontal treatment is to stop this progressive destruction by controlling infection, thus preventing tooth loss. However, periodontal pockets associated with intrabony defect (IBD) often remain, even after nonsurgical periodontal treatment (NSPT), thus increasing the risk of disease progression and worsening the prognosis. Therefore, surgical intervention is often considered a valid option. Current evidence shows the potential for tissue formation in IBD treated with guided tissue regeneration (GTR) using biological membranes placed for treating the affected site. This acts as a guide for the healing process [2].

Traditional treatments for periodontitis, such as patient education, oral hygiene instructions, scaling, root planing, and in certain cases, periodontal surgery or the use of chemotherapeutic agents, have been the cornerstone of managing this pervasive disease. Despite these efforts, the quest for enhanced recovery outcomes has led to the exploration of innovative materials and techniques in periodontal regeneration [3].

Among these innovative approaches, the application of a Triphasic Hyaluronan-Chitosan-Strontium Chloride membrane has emerged as a promising strategy for the treatment of periodontal intrabony defects. Each component of this triphasic system brings unique properties that are beneficial to the regenerative process [4].

Chitosan, a biocompatible and biodegradable polysaccharide, is lauded for its antimicrobial properties and its ability to facilitate bone formation, owing to its structural resemblance to glycosaminoglycans. This makes it an excellent scaffold material for drug delivery and tissue regeneration [5].

Hyaluronic acid, a key component of the extracellular matrix in connective tissues, plays a crucial role in wound healing. Its high molecular weight contributes to tissue hydration and facilitates cell migration, essential for the repair and regeneration of periodontal tissues. Its ability to modulate inflammation and promote angiogenesis further underscores its importance in creating a conducive environment for tissue repair [6].

Strontium Chloride, known for its osteogenic properties, enhances bone regeneration through the stimulation of periodontal ligament stem cells and the promotion of bone formation. Its inclusion in periodontal therapy can lead to significant improvements in clinical outcomes, such as reduced pocket depth and increased attachment levels, offering a new dimension to regenerative periodontal treatment [7].

Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of the combined effect of Chitosan, hyaluronan, and strontium chloride membranes in the treatment of periodontal intrabony defect.

Patients and Methods:

This research was a clinical, two-arm, and actively controlled, parallel-group randomized controlled trial. This study was carried out on 36 patients with an age range between 25 and 55 years. The patients were selected from the outpatient clinic of the Oral Medicine and Periodontology Department, Faculty of Dentistry, October 6 University.

After being reviewed and accepted by the Center of Evidence-Based Dentistry- 6 October University, the study protocol and the template form written informed consent were approved by the Research Ethics Committee, Faculty of Dentistry, 6 October University.

Inclusion criteria were patient having stage II to III periodontitis with probing pocket depths ≥ 5 mm and radiographic evidence showing infra bony defect, Grade B periodontitis, systemically healthy individuals, a probing depth of more than 5 mm after phase 1 therapy, pocket depth is measured and if more than 5 mm, the surgery was done, compliant patients who follow oral hygiene instructions.

Exclusion criteria were patients received periodontal or antibiotic therapy within the previous 6 months preceding the study, smoker patients, pregnant and lactating females, patients on medications are known to affect bone turnover.

The patients were divided into two equal groups as follows: **Group A (Control group):** patients were treated with open flap debridement and **group B (Test group):** patients were treated surgically with hyaluronan, chitosan, and strontium chloride membrane.

METHODS

Membrane preparation

Membrane components were: Chitosan, Strontium Chloride, Hyaluronic acid powder, Glycolic Acid 70%, and Sodium hydroxide. All reagents and chemicals were of analytical grade. Water used throughout the entire work was distilled water.

The Chitosan, Hyaluronic acid, and Strontium Chloride membranes were prepared using freeze extraction ^[8]. The gelation method used by Ho et al. was implemented at the materials science department, Institute of Graduate Studies and Research, Alexandria University ^[9].

Surgical procedures:

Presurgical protocol:

Before the surgery, Patients eligible for the study were screened by a comprehensive periodontal examination, and full periodontal charts were obtained. Periapical radiographs were taken for periodontitis patients, at sites of attachment loss for diagnosis of the case. After the initial examination, all patients were motivated to perform personal oral hygiene measures using soft toothbrushes and interdental cleansing devices. Each patient underwent full mouth supra and sub-gingival debridement. All the previously listed clinical evaluations were examined to ascertain the suitability of the participants for the trials and the need for the surgery.

The following measurements were evaluated for each patient:

Plaque index (PI): The plaque index assesses the amount of dental plaque visible on the vestibular and lingual surfaces of all teeth, except the third molars. A mouth mirror and an explorer were used after air drying of teeth and gingiva to assess plaque. Four areas of the teeth (distofacial, facial, mesiofacial and lingual surfaces) were examined

systematically with criteria from 0 to 3. 0: no plaque, 1: separate flecks of plaque at the cervical margin of the tooth, 2: a thin continuous band of plaque (up to 1 mm) at the cervical margin of the tooth and 4: a band of plaque wider than 1 mm but covering less than one-third of the crown of the tooth.

Bone sounding: measuring from the closest cusp tip of the involved tooth to the base of the defect (as a reference point) and the bone level of the defect using an incipient probe (15 mm).

Radiographic examination

Was performed just before the surgery using a size 2 imaging plate (Guilin wood pecker medical instrument COLTD) and dental x-ray machine which was set as 70 kvp, 8 MA, and 0.08-0.04 s, the intra-oral radiograph was captured using a paralleling technique with kcp film hddc.

Surgical protocol

The envelope flap was started as an intrasulcular incision using the number 15 blade. The incision extended from the mid-buccal surface of the tooth mesial to the involved tooth to the mid-buccal surface of the tooth distal to the involved tooth. The flap was reflected buccally using a mucco periosteal elevator. If the required accessibility was not achieved, then the palatal or lingual flap was reflected with the same extension as the buccal one. The flap was reflected to expose 2mm of bone apical to the defect base after flap elevation root planing was performed for the involved tooth with universal curette removing soft and infected cementum as well as granulation tissue, a superficial-layer split-thickness flap was performed which provided maximal flap release and mobilization for coronal positioning, The superficial-layer split-thickness flap technique dissects following the contour of the external surface of the flap, toward the lip or cheek, and separates the epithelium and connective tissue from the underlying muscular and periosteal layers, which remain attached to the bone that allows complete, passive flap coverage for virtually all root. Then the membrane was applied in the area of the intrabony defect after contouring the external border using a surgical successor to be rounded and it was avoided to have any sharp edges as possible taking into consideration the dimension of the defect using a template, the application of the membrane was easy with no need for using any cementing material or more sutures for fixation.

Sutures were used to stabilize the coronal displacement of the buccal flap. The envelop incisions were closed with interrupted sutures ^[10-13].

Methods of Clinical Evaluation:

Patients were recalled 1 week and 2 weeks after surgery (for gingival index). The following clinical parameters were evaluated for every patient included in the study, at 3 and at 6 months after treatment ^[14, 15]: Gingival index (GI) according to Loe and Silness (1963). Clinical attachment level (CAL). Periodontal probing depth (PD) according to Glavind and Loe (1967) using acrylic stent for pocket assessment.

Radiographic measurements were performed at phase 1 therapy and then at 3 and 6 months after surgery. Radiographs were taken using Digital Periapical X-ray. The radiographic measurements to be included are as follows: The level of the bone height was measured from the cemento enamel junction to the base of the bony defect. Also, bone sounding was repeated 3 and 6 months after surgery.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done by SPSS v26 (IBM Inc., Armonk, NY, USA). Quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation (SD), and the two groups were compared utilizing unpaired Student's t-test and compared between different readings utilizing the ANOVA (F) test. Qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentage (%) and were analyzed utilizing the Chi-square test. A two-tailed P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Demographic data (Age and sex) were insignificantly different between both groups. The clinical attachment loss was significantly reduced after 3 months and after 6 months compared to baseline in group A and in group B (P <0.001), while The clinical attachment loss was insignificantly different between both groups at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months in both groups. **Table 1**

Table 1: Demographics of the studied groups, Comparing clinical attachment loss at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months between the two groups

		Group A (n=18)		Group B (n=18)		P value	
Age (years)		33.5 ± 9.51		31.1 ± 7.93		0.430	
Gender	Male	9 (50%)		5 (27.78%)		0.171	
	Female	9 (50%)		13 (72.22%)			
		Baseline	After 3 months	After 6 months	P value	Post Hoc	
Clinical attachment loss (Group A)		5.9 ± 0.35	0.3 ± 0.36	0.2 ± 0.32	<0.001*	P1<0.001* P2<0.001* P3=NS	
Clinical attachment loss							
Clinical attachment loss (Group B)		6.2 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	<0.001*	P1<0.001* P2<0.001* P3=NS	
Group A (n=18)		5.9 ± 0.35	0.3 ± 0.36	0.2 ± 0.32	NS		
Group B (n=18)		6.2 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	NS		

Data is expressed as the mean ±SD, P1: P-value comparing baseline reading and after 3 months reading, P2: P-value comparing baseline reading and after 6 months reading, P3: P-value comparing after 3 months reading and after 6 months reading.

In group A, pain was significantly reduced at all durations compared to D1 (P<0.001). Pain was significantly reduced at D3, D4, D5, D6, and D7 compared to D2 (P<0.001). Pain was insignificantly different among D3, D4, D5, D6, and D7. In group B, pain was significantly reduced at all durations compared to D1 (P<0.001). Pain was significantly

reduced at D3, D4, D5, D6, and D7 compared to D2 ($P < 0.001$). Pain was insignificantly different among D3, D4, D5, D6, and D7. The pain was significantly reduced in group B compared to group A at D1 and D2 ($P < 0.001$), while the remaining durations were insignificantly different between both groups. **Table 2**

Table 2: Pain in group A and B at different durations and Comparing pain at different durations between the two groups

		D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	P value	
Pain (Group A)	Mean $\pm$ SD	7.6 $\pm$ 0.61	4.4 $\pm$ 0.62	1.1 $\pm$ 0.24	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	<0.001*	
	Post hoc	P1	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*		<0.001*
		P2	<0.001*		<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*		
		P3				0.332	0.332	0.332		0.332
		P4					NS	NS		NS
		P5						NS		NS
		P6								NS
		D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	P value	
Pain (Group B)	Mean $\pm$ SD	6.6 $\pm$ 0.62	3.3 $\pm$ 0.57	1.1 $\pm$ 0.24	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	<0.001*	
	Post hoc	P1	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*		<0.001*
		P2	<0.001*		<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*	<0.001*		
		P3				0.331	0.331	0.331		0.331
		P4					NS	NS		NS
		P5						NS		NS
		P6								NS
Group A (n=18)	Mean $\pm$ SD	7.6 $\pm$ 0.61	4.4 $\pm$ 0.62	1.1 $\pm$ 0.24	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	---	
Group B (n=18)	Mean $\pm$ SD	6.6 $\pm$ 0.62	3.3 $\pm$ 0.57	1.1 $\pm$ 0.24	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	---	
P-value		<0.001*	<0.001*	0.968	NS	NS	NS	NS	---	

P1: P-value comparing D1 reading and the remaining readings, P2: P-value comparing D2 reading and the remaining readings, P3: P-value comparing D3 reading and the remaining readings, P4: P-value comparing D4 reading and the remaining readings, P5: P-value comparing D5 reading and the remaining readings, P6: P-value comparing D6 reading and D7 reading. *: significant P value.

The swelling score was insignificantly different between both groups at different durations. **Table 3**

Table 3: Swelling score in each studied group at different durations, Comparing swelling scores at different durations between the two groups

	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6	D7	P value
Swelling Score (Group A)	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	NS
Swelling Score (Group B)	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	NS
Group A (n=18)	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	----
Group B (n=18)	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	1 $\pm$ 0	----
P-value	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	-----

Data is expressed as the mean $\pm$ SD,

The gingival index was significantly reduced after 3 months and after 6 months compared to baseline in group A and in group B ($P < 0.001$), while the gingival index was insignificantly different after 3 months and after 6 months in both groups. **Table 4**

Table 4: Gingival index in each of the studied groups at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months

	Baseline	After 3 months	After 6 months	P value	Post Hoc
Gingival index (Group A)	2.6 ± 0.15	0.7 ± 0.46	0.6 ± 0.5	<0.001*	P1<0.001* P2<0.001* P3=0.16
Gingival index (Group B)	2.1 ± 0.5	0.4 ± 0.51	0.3 ± 0.49	<0.001*	P1<0.001* P2<0.001* P3=0.16
Gingival index	Baseline	After 3 months	After 6 months		
Group A (n=18)	2.6 ± 0.15	0.7 ± 0.46	0.6 ± 0.5		
Group B (n=18)	2.4 ± 0.5	0.4 ± 0.51	0.3 ± 0.49		
P-value	1	0.096	0.1		

Data is expressed as the mean ±SD, P1: P-value comparing baseline reading and after 3 months reading, P2: P-value comparing baseline reading and after 6 months reading, P3: P-value comparing after 3 months reading and after 6 months reading.

The radiographic bone level was insignificantly different at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months in the two studied groups. **Table 5**

Table 5: Radiographic bone level in each of the studied groups at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months and Comparing radiographic bone level at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months between the two groups

	Baseline	After 3 months	After 6 months	P value
Radiographic bone level (Group A)	5 ± 0.43	5 ± 0.12	4.9 ± 0.86	0.996
Radiographic bone level (Group B)	5.11 ± 0.75	5 ± 0.75	5 ± 0.74	0.996
Group A (n=18)	5 ± 0.43	5 ± 0.12	4.9 ± 0.68	---
Group B (n=18)	5.11 ± 0.75	5 ± 0.75	5 ± 0.74	----
P-value	NS	NS	NS	---

Data is expressed as the mean ±SD,

The probing depth was significantly reduced after 3 months and after 6 months compared to baseline in group A and in group B (P<0.001), while probing depth was insignificantly different after 3 months and after 6 months in both groups. The Probing depth was insignificantly different between both groups at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months. **Table 6**

Table 6: Comparing probing depth at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months between the two groups and Comparing Probing depth at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months between the two groups

	Baseline	After 3 months	After 6 months	P value
Probing depth (Group A)	6.2 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	<0.001* P1<0.001* P2<0.001* P3=NS
Probing depth (Group B)	6.2 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	<0.001* P1<0.001*

				P2<0.001* P3=NS
Group A (n=18)	6.2 ± 0.38	0.3 ± 0.25	0.2 ± 0.25	----
Group B (n=18)	6.2 ± 0.38	0.3 ± 0.38	0.2 ± 0.38	----
P-value	NS	NS	NS	----

Data is expressed as the mean ±SD

DISCUSSION

Periodontitis stands as a principal cause of tooth loss. Where a progressive inflammatory disease affects the periodontium, triggering an immune response that leads to the deterioration of the teeth's supportive structures [1].

The current study found that the gingival index was significantly reduced after 3 months and after 6 months compared to baseline in group A and in group B ($P < 0.001$), while the gingival index was insignificantly different after 3 months and after 6 months in both groups. The gingival index was insignificantly different between both groups at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months.

Mahmoud et al., evaluated the clinical, radiographic, and biochemical effects of 1% chitosan gel in the treatment of chronic periodontitis patients and included 20 patients divided into two groups using the split-mouth technique. Group A: consisted of 30 sides that received SRP with intrapocket application of 1% chitosan gel. Group B: consisted of 30 sides that received SRP only. The results of that study showed a statistically significant difference in gingival index between study groups in favor of the test group. The use of the gel form of Chitosan gel has sustained release property which may prolong the effect of the material, Hence, the difference in the gingival index between study groups [16].

The difference in the results between Mahmoud et al study and the current study may be due to two factors: a) the sample size in Mahmoud et al study was larger compared to the current study, and the use of the gel form of Chitosan which has sustained release properties that could be responsible for more prolonged time for the material to act upon the tissue during the healing phase.

The results of the current study regarding GI coincide with a study evaluating the effect of HA versus SRP in the treatment of vertical bone loss in periodontitis patients clinically and radiographically. In this study researchers reported that the mean value of the gingival index (GI) for the HA group at the baseline before surgery was 1.48 ± 0.25 , after 3 months after surgery it was 0.633 ± 0.12 while after 6 months it was 0.60 ± 0.10 . For the SRP group, it was 1.52 ± 0.29 at the baseline before surgery, after 3 months it was 0.671 ± 0.11 while after 6 months it was 0.46 ± 0.18 [17].

In our results, the PPD was significantly reduced after 3 months and after 6 months compared to baseline in group A and in group B ($P < 0.001$), while PPD was insignificantly different after 3 months and after 6 months in both groups. The PPD was insignificantly different between both groups at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months.

In harmony, a study on the treatment of intrabony defects by Faghani et al. utilized chitosan versus SRP. They found that mean PPD significantly decreased in chitosan and SRP groups between baseline and follow-up ($P < 0.05$). There was no significant difference in the pre-surgical PPD between both groups ($P = 0.316$). Also, there was no significant difference in PPD at follow-up ($P = 0.133$) between both groups [18].

In our results, the clinical attachment loss was significantly reduced after 3 months and after 6 months compared to baseline in group A and in group B ($P < 0.001$), while clinical attachment loss was insignificantly different after 3 months and after 6 months in both groups. The clinical attachment loss was insignificantly different between both groups at baseline, after 3 months, and after 6 months.

Faghani et al., also revealed that CAL improved in all groups between baseline and follow-up. No significant difference was observed among the groups at baseline ($P = 0.402$) and at follow-up ($P = 0.953$). However, in all groups, the difference in CAL was significant before and after surgery ($P < 0.05$) [18].

This study was in contradiction with Meenakshi and Sankari who showed that both groups- (group 1 received open flap debridement with bone graft as a control group, and group 2 received open flap debridement with bone graft mixed with a chitosan nano hydrogel)- exhibited a significant reduction in probing pocket depths and CAL at six months. The mean reduction in probing depths in group 2 (test group) was significantly higher (8.3 ± 0.9 to 1.6 ± 0.8) when compared to group 1 (8 ± 0.8 to 2.3 ± 0.7). The mean reduction in CAL in group 2 (8.7 ± 0.6 to 1.6 ± 0.8) was significantly higher than that of group 1 (8.6 ± 0.5 to 2.4 ± 0.7). This difference may be attributed to the added benefit of the use of bone grafts [19].

Using a Chitosan membrane, a study was performed to evaluate the effectiveness of a chitosan nano hydrogel as a periodontal regenerative material in the management of intrabony defects, this study included 20 patients who were randomly divided into the control group, where defects were filled with bovine particulate graft (osseograft), and the test group, where the defects were filled with bovine particulate grafts mixed with a chitosan hydrogel and found that mean amount of defect fills observed in group-1 (3.5 ± 0.5 to 2.3 ± 0.4) and group-2 (3.7 ± 0.6 to 1.8 ± 0.4) from baseline to six months was recorded. Statistically significant differences in the amount of defect fill were observed between the two groups at six months [19]. The combination of bone graft and Chitosan in the form of nanogel may have a beneficial effect over the use of Chitosan without a space provision material such as bone graft.

In using the Strontium Chloride membrane, Strontium, Sr, an alkaline earth metal, is an important trace element in the human body. It has interesting properties and is chemically similar to calcium, thus, it can substitute calcium in the bone matrix relatively easily. It has been found to induce osteoblast activity by stimulating bone formation and reducing bone resorption. Moreover, in several studies, it has been reported to stimulate osteogenic differentiation and proliferation in mesenchymal stem cells and osteoblasts [20].

Recently, Kim et al. concluded that Chitosan's ability to support bone formation is attributed to its structural similarity to glycosaminoglycans, facilitating osteoblast proliferation and differentiation. Additionally, chitosan can act as a carrier for controlled drug release, the results of the present study demonstrated that chitosan showed significant improvement in clinical parameters in the same group. These results were consistent with other studies that used 1% chitosan gel and reported a significant reduction of probing depth, improvement in CAL and bone level at six months [21].

The hyaluronic acid component ensures optimal tissue hydration and inflammation modulation, chitosan provides a microbial-resistant scaffold that supports tissue and bone formation, and Strontium Chloride enhances bone regeneration and strength [22]

CONCLUSIONS

The use of triphasic Hyaluronan – Chitosan – Strontium Chloride membrane in conjunction with periodontal flap surgery in treating intrabony defect did not show a statistically significant difference in comparison to OFD alone. Regarding periodontal probing depth, clinical attachment loss, gingival index, and radiographic bone fill, there was an improvement in both groups. Moreover, tissue response to the triphasic Hyaluronan -Chitosan- Strontium Chloride membrane was favorable as reflected by reduced pain and swelling.

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Conflict of Interest: Nil

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